

The impact of digitalization level on job satisfaction and employee performance in the airport industry^{‡§}

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p>	<p>Although technology, which entered the world with the dawn of industrialization, has had a tremendously positive effect on humanity across a wide range of domains, it must innovate and evolve continuously to maintain its competitive edge in the face of shifting circumstances. The digitalization process, initiated by technological advancements, has given rise to intensified competition among various sectors. In such a competitive environment, characterized by its destructive nature, it is imperative for professionals to possess a comprehensive understanding of the latest technological advancements, to employ these innovations in the most efficacious manner, and to facilitate the assimilation of technological innovations by employees. This is essential for the effective execution of activities within the airport industry, as well as in other sectors. The digitalization process is of critical importance to the air transportation industry, as well as to all other industries. The present study, therefore, focuses on the approaches of airport employees to digitalization processes. Furthermore, the impact of digitalization on employee productivity and satisfaction in the context of airports is examined. The study utilized the Digital Transformation Readiness Survey scale developed by the Center for Creative Leadership-Corporate Leaders, as well as scales designed to measure employee productivity and satisfaction, in order to ascertain the impact of digitalization on these two key areas. The present study examined the question of whether demographic characteristics have a significant impact on employee productivity, satisfaction and digitalization level. The results of the study indicated a partial significant effect. The findings of the regression analysis suggest that the level of digitalization exerts a significant influence on employee productivity. Furthermore, the results indicate that employee satisfaction plays a mediating role in the relationship between employee productivity and the digitalization process.</p>
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1. Introduction

The concept of digitalization is derived from the Latin word 'digitus', which translates to 'finger' and is associated with meanings such as 'number' and 'digit' in European languages (Baloğlu, 2023). Digitalization is a novel generation approach that has disseminated rapidly in the globalizing world, with the impact of the industrial revolution, and affects almost every aspect of life. Digitalization is undergoing continuous development, progressing through successive phases, with each new phase accompanied by emergent concepts, in a period characterized by accelerated production and consumption (Baloğlu, 2023). In the extant literature, the concept of digitalization is expressed as the transfer of the information and hardware of the organization to the virtual environment with the use of electronic devices by converting them into digital data (Baloğlu, 2023). In the contemporary business landscape, digital transformation is regarded as an unavoidable phenomenon, permeating all facets of an enterprise's operations. This phenomenon also facilitates the integration of digitalization into novel management methodologies. The advantages of digitalization are manifold, including the enhancement of information availability, the acceleration of production and workflow, the protection and storage of information, and the reduction of costs through digital storage conditions. However, as with any new approach, it is not without its inherent limitations, which include concerns regarding security, the prevalence of cybercrime, and the emergence of online threats. Nevertheless, it is anticipated that these challenges will be addressed in a timely manner through advancements in technology (Üzmez & Büyükbeşe, 2021).

The concept of employee satisfaction emerged as a distinct field of study in the 1920s, coinciding with the development of job satisfaction as a scholarly domain. The 1930-1940 Neoclassical management approach influenced this paradigm shift, and its impact was recognized within organizations and in the relevant literature. Consequently, studies on the subject began to be carried out (Çabukel, 2008). These studies gave rise to numerous definitions. These definitions can be succinctly expressed as 'the feeling of happiness that arouses the employee's commitment to their job and organizational environment' or 'the extent to which employees feel harmonious with their work and work environment' (Korkmaz & Erdoğan, 2014). The outcomes of these studies have indicated that employee satisfaction engenders a number of benefits for employers, including the promotion of organizational continuity, enhanced commitment to the organization, elevated motivation levels, and the optimization of employee performance. In addition to the employee-enterprise benefit relationship, it is also important to observe that the business-employee benefit relationship is also important. The effectiveness and efficiency with which a business operates is directly correlated with its ability to provide motivating and satisfying benefits to its employees. Consequently, it can be concluded that employee satisfaction is a pivotal aspect for both the business and its workforce (Korkmaz & Erdoğan, 2014).

Employee productivity is a proportional performance measure, the calculation of which is based on the ratio of inputs to outputs. Conceptually, it can be expressed as the utilization of the full performance of the employee in a manner that ensures continuity at a level that will provide the highest benefit to the organization (Özçelik & Kandemir, 2017). Performance and productivity are pivotal criteria in the assessment of employee productivity. In addition to performance and productivity, the time spent in performing the job is another important criterion. In the contemporary business landscape, there is a discernible trend towards enhancing productivity levels in order to maintain a competitive edge within the industry. In this context, the emphasis on achieving low-cost and high-quality output has emerged as a pivotal factor in maintaining competitive advantage (Kıraç, 2024).

The definitions also exert an influence on each other within the organization. Increases in employee satisfaction have been shown to result in corresponding increases in productivity, while decreases in satisfaction have been demonstrated to lead to declines in productivity. The sense of satisfaction that employees experience fosters a sense of ownership over the organization, which in turn is believed to positively impact productivity by encouraging employees to derive fulfilment from their work (Ulusoy & Tınar, 2017). Conversely, when employees are discontented, they are less inclined to perform their duties with enthusiasm, their sense of belonging to the organization is diminished, and consequently, there may be a significant decline in performance. However, it should be noted that employee

satisfaction is subject to variation depending on factors such as life view, motivational tools, and personality (Eceoğlu, 2020).

A review of the extant literature on the digitalization of airports reveals the impact of the global pandemic of Coronavirus on the digital transformation of such facilities (Kováčiková et al., 2022), comparison of the digitalization of Slovak airports within the scope of digital transformation of European Union countries (Kovacikova et al, 2021), the potential impact of digital technologies on modernization and cost reduction at regional airports (Remencová & Sedláčková, 2021), the productivity of airports with tools such as vza and Malmquist (Asker & Yaşar, 2018), segmentation of passenger preferences for using digital technologies at Norwegian airports (Halpern, Mwesiumo, Budd, et al., 2021), and the impact of organizational readiness, innovation, airport size and ownership on digital change at airports (Halpernet et al., 2021). Conversely, there is an absence of research examining the impact of digitalization on employee performance and productivity in the context of airports. The present study is unique in this respect. In the context of VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity) environments, which characterize contemporary business landscapes, airports must optimize their operational efficiency in a competitive environment. The integration of digitalization into their structures is imperative for achieving this objective. Digitalization has been demonstrated to increase employee satisfaction and alleviate the workload in the organizational work environment. Conversely, an enhancement in employee satisfaction has been shown to engender an increase in productivity. In this case, it can be predicted that the digitalization level of the airport has a direct effect on employee satisfaction and employee productivity. It is anticipated that this study will contribute to the extant literature and serve as a foundation for future research.

The primary objective of the research is to underscore the significance of digitalization for the advancement of airports, as is the case in all sectors. Additionally, the study aims to ascertain the impact of digitalization on employee satisfaction and productivity. The primary objectives of the study focused on the uncertainty determined by the main objectives and sub-objectives. In alignment with the sub-objectives;

- The extent to which airport employees exhibit resistance to digitalization,
- The presence of a lack of trust among employees in digital systems,
- Employees' attitudes towards digital technologies,
- The sufficiency of the company's level of digitalization,
- The impact of digitalization on employees,
- The extent to which digitalization is internalized by employees,
- The impact of digitalization on the productivity of employees.

The research question is determined in line with the objectives and seeks answers to the following questions:

- What is the level of digitalization of airport employees?
- Does the level of digitalization affect employee productivity and satisfaction?
- Does the digitalization process differ according to various categorical variables?

The remainder of the research is organized as follows. Initially, the extant literature was reviewed to identify studies pertinent to the subject. The subsequent stage of the research process involved the presentation of the methodology employed in the study. This section entails the population and sample of the study, the formulation of hypotheses, the elaboration of the questionnaire form employed in the study, and the methodology of data analysis. The fourth section comprises the presentation of results and associated discussions. This section is where the findings are interpreted and the validation of the hypotheses is evaluated. The final section of the study comprises the conclusions and recommendations.

2. Previous Studies

In this study, the impact of digitalization on employee satisfaction and productivity at airports is examined. A broad literature review was conducted in the first stage. In this context, studies on the impact of digitalization on employee satisfaction and productivity in different industries were included.

Öztemiz (2005) revealed that stress in the business world has destructive effects on employees and the functioning of the organization in the light of the literatures and data examined. He categorized stressors into work-related, non-work-related, and individual categories, and included a table outlining the potential consequences of stress in his study. Moreover, a comprehensive review of extant literature on these subjects was undertaken. The findings of the studies reviewed indicated that elevated levels of stress among employees can lead to a decline in productivity and a deterioration in organizational efficiency. However, it is imperative for organizations to implement effective measures to mitigate stress levels among their employees and to manage stress effectively, thereby averting the adverse consequences outlined above.

In their study on the effect of work stress on employee satisfaction, Kaplan et al. (2018) predicted that contemporary technologies are employed effectively in the field of health, yet simultaneously increase work stress while alleviating the workload. The survey technique was utilized within the scope of the research. The questionnaire was administered to employees of a public hospital in Istanbul. The researchers were unable to draw a general conclusion about the impact of job stress on employee satisfaction due to two limitations. Firstly, the employees did not dedicate sufficient time to answering the questionnaire. Secondly, the study was limited to a single public organization. Nevertheless, the study provides a foundation for future research.

Taşel (2020) furthermore noted in his research that technology facilitates customers' access to information, as evidenced by various literature data. However, it is predicted that increasing innovations have entered the structuring of economic activities on the journey from physical trade to e-commerce. It was further noted that digitalization has become pervasive in this process, particularly in light of the ongoing pandemic, and the positive impact this has had on e-commerce.

In his study, Çankaya (2020) investigated the benefits of digital materials used at the airport. Moreover, the study goes on to explore the various domains in which these technologies are employed within the context of airports. It is predicted that API technologies will accelerate the development of airports. The study also posits that robots, which are among the digital tools, can understand the problems and requests of passengers during their journey and accelerate the service process. The study also examined the role of the Schiphol Airport robot, named Spencer, which has been designed to minimize passenger anxiety regarding locating the departure gate. The robot's function is twofold: it assists with passenger navigation by offering marketing products while they are searching for the gate, thereby contributing to both operational efficiency and economic development at the airport.

Ersöz et al. (2020) emphasized in their study that technology is an inevitable phenomenon in the current era. They emphasized the importance of Information Technology (IT) technologies for employees in terms of information sharing, workload facilitation, data storage and data sharing. Moreover, the assertion that the prevalence of advanced technology applications necessarily leads to an increase in employee unemployment is demonstrably false. Consequently, they concluded that the integration of technology into organizational systems will enhance employee performance.

Atar (2020) stated in his study that digitalization is a significant factor in the development of the tourism sector, as in every sector. The study examined the relevant literature on the subject. It was emphasized that personnel who are digitally literate, having received the necessary training, are better able to convey their experiences to passengers. This, in turn, has the potential to increase customer satisfaction and preference. The findings of the research indicate that customer attraction strategies involving the dissemination of advertising content on social media are now increasing the number of customers at a reduced cost. It is further reported that the tourism sector employs technology in a competent and effective manner.

Türkay and Artar (2021) conducted a study on the impact of digitalization on employees. The researchers emphasized that for the future of organizations, digitalization should support the

adaptation of employees to the digitalization process, customer satisfaction, and employees should receive support in terms of all kinds of information and technology that can be used in the digitalization journey. The study also emphasized the importance of organizations supporting their investments in R&D, concluding that the concept of IT is a significant value in today's world. However, it was noted that employees often have misperceptions about IT and that its adoption is not sufficient despite its intertwining with technology. It is predicted that measures must be taken to address the employment challenges faced by organizations and employees in an increasingly competitive environment. Consequently, it is proposed that the provision of technology training and the enhancement of awareness concerning IT applications will result in an augmentation of production and development.

Yorulmaz's (2021) study sought to ascertain the perceptions and expectations of port managers operating in Turkey towards the concept of digitalization. The study also highlighted the significance of digitalization for ports and the managers who work in them. In alignment with this notion, a questionnaire study was conducted to ascertain the expectations from digitalization in port enterprises, and an interview technique was also employed. The analysis of the survey responses indicated that the technological capabilities employed in Turkish port enterprises are inadequate for ensuring the effective operation of these facilities. It was observed that the majority of port managers acknowledged the necessity for digitalization in port operations, yet concerns regarding costs and adaptability were also expressed. It has been asserted that digitalization is imperative for enhancing port operations, promoting speed, efficiency and safety. It has been emphasized that for port enterprises to thrive in a dynamic sector, to keep pace with evolving changes and to address the escalating demands, it is essential to closely monitor technological advancements and to integrate them into their structures.

Sucu (2021) conducted a study to ascertain the correlation between employees' compliance with digitalization activities and organizational climate. A survey technique was employed, and the study encompassed 183 employees utilizing the digital programs of ground handling companies servicing aircraft in the apron area of Istanbul Airport. The findings of the correlation analysis indicated the presence of a positive relationship between employees' compliance with digitalization activities and organizational climate. The regression analysis further predicted that organizational climate exerts a significant influence on digitalization compliance. The results of the ANOVA test indicated that high school graduates exhibited a greater propensity for digitalization activities in comparison to university graduates. Within the context of the adaptation of employees to digitalization activities, the t-test was utilized to assess the impact of gender on this adaptation, but it did not attain statistical significance. Finally, it was concluded that employees can carry out their activities positively in organizations with high levels of morale, motivation and desire.

In this study, Yavaş (2022) sought to elucidate the impact of Industry 4.0 and associated themes on the aviation sector. To this end, a comprehensive analysis of extant academic literature was conducted, with a particular focus on the nexus between digitalization and productivity in the aviation industry. As a methodological approach, the author listed the results on the keywords 'Aviation, Digital and Productivity' in the Web of Science and Scopus databases. The WOS Viewer software was then used to visualize the matching of keywords with each other. The analysis revealed that the keywords 'digital twin, Internet of Things, technology, artificial intelligence, innovation' emerged as particularly salient, underscoring the prevalence of the concept of 'digital twin' within this domain. The evaluation of the studies was also based on this concept.

Güzel and Salimbayeva (2022) conducted an examination of the primary trends of Almaty airport with regard to digitalization, as the accelerated development of technology in the globalizing world is also reflected in airports. Moreover, the article reviews the most advanced technologies for airports and examines the technologies employed in airport services at Almaty airport. The study incorporated a comprehensive review of the extant literature, complemented by quantitative data analysis. This comprehensive approach yielded several key trends. These include self-automation, artificial intelligence, cyber security, biometrics and robotic assistants. The study went on to make future forecasts for Almaty Airport, covering topics such as ADS-B (Automatic Dependent Monitoring-Broadcasting), IoT (Internet of Things) and RFID (Radio Frequency Identification). The researchers

identified price, quality, speed, trust, safety and technological knowledge as the primary factors influencing these forecasts.

Demiral (2022) conducted a periodic examination of the aviation sector, delineating the following periods: (aviation 1.0) the era characterized by the challenges associated with technological access and utilization, wherein technological materials were integrated into aircraft design; (aviation 2.0) the period marked by the emergence of ground-direction tracking, the consideration of weather conditions, the utilization of devices in inclement weather, and the density of air traffic areas; and (aviation 3.0), the production of new types of aircraft, the establishment of airline companies and the transition from a complex cockpit structure to an understandable and simple cockpit, and the current period (aviation 4.0), which is the period in which the transition to the digital environment where advanced technological moves are made using big data is realized. It has been emphasized that aviation 4.0 is not a matter of desire but a necessity in order for aviation to progress dynamically rather than in a stable way, to constantly renew itself in a difficult competitive environment, to keep up with technology and to use technological materials in the most effective way.

Yüksel et al. (2022) conducted a study on the assessment of digital transformation risks at airports. Initially, a comprehensive analysis of the risks encountered in digital transformation and the extant literature was conducted. It is hypothesized that the implementation of multi-criteria decision-making methods in the evaluation of alternatives will yield more efficacious outcomes. The study's findings revealed a significant financial burden associated with digital transformation risks in the airport sector. The objective of this study is to assess the risks associated with digital transformation in Turkish airports. Initially, the findings were analyzed using the fishbone method to identify the risk factors. These factors were then grouped according to their criteria. It is anticipated that by identifying these risks, the necessary steps can be taken to facilitate the digital transformation process. The study's findings have also prompted the recommendation that similar research be conducted in airports in other countries, facilitating cross-country comparisons and enhancing the general understanding of risk factors.

Meydan (2023) conducted a study into the digital applications utilized by airline companies, exploring the manner in which novel digital technologies are integrated with the applications currently in use. The novel technologies encompassed in the scope of this research are as follows: Blockchain, augmented reality and virtual reality, artificial intelligence, sign technology, robotics, biometrics, big data and analytics, machine learning, the Internet of Things (IoT), RFID and barcode-based tracking, GPS tracking, wearable devices, and smart sensors. Utilizing value chain analysis, Meydan concluded that airline companies are endeavoring to employ new digital technologies.

In this research, Üzel (2023) concentrated on hot air ballooning, a specific form of general aviation. Üzel emphasized that the 1900s stand out in terms of the history of the hot air balloon. The objective of the present study is to elucidate the digitalization process in the business use of hot air balloons, which are regarded as primitive. The geographical scope of the study is confined to the Cappadocia region in Turkey, with a particular emphasis on the digitalization processes within Gökçen Aviation, a company that operates within this region. The study utilized an interview technique, a qualitative research method, to gather data. The research findings indicate that digitalization in the context of hot air balloon activities is predominantly focused on communication, customer acquisition, and flight record management.

Göçmen (2024) conducted a study that compared the innovation practices of airports. The study incorporated an examination of innovation classification and contemporary airport management approaches. The study utilized data from the Airports Association International to analyze the innovation strategies and common characteristics of the three airports with the highest passenger traffic worldwide in 2022. The analysis revealed that airports have predominantly implemented measures to enhance customer experience and operational processes, environmental sustainability, and energy efficiency. The study further emphasized the pivotal role of strategy adoption and collaborative efforts in ensuring the effective implementation of innovative solutions.

Elçi (2024) conducted a field study in the civil aviation sector to examine the mediating role of digital leadership in the impact of digital transformation on employee behaviors. The study examined the impact of digital leadership practices on the behavioral dynamics of employees in the civil aviation

sector. The study emphasizes the critical importance of digital transformation and demonstrates how employee adaptation plays an important role in the transformation process. The primary objective of the study is to ascertain the impact of digital transformation initiatives at İGA Istanbul Airport Operation on employee job satisfaction, job performance and turnover intention. The study emphasizes the significance of digital transformation approaches and aims to raise awareness of digital leadership in the aviation sector. The study's findings indicate that supportive leadership plays a pivotal role in digital transformation processes, and that digitalization has a positive impact on job performance and job satisfaction.

Çıkmaz et al. (2024) aimed to reveal the importance of technological readiness in the impact of new technological developments and digital application presentations on customer experience in the aviation industry. The study utilized a face-to-face survey administered to 1,328 participants residing in Istanbul, Antalya, Nevşehir and Gaziantep provinces. Three distinct scales were utilized in the survey, and confirmatory factor analysis was employed to analyze the data. The study's findings indicated that the digital services provided by airlines have a positive impact on the tourist experience. Furthermore, it was observed that the digital readiness levels of the participants played a moderating role in their experience of these digital services.

3. Methodology

This study constitutes an applied and cross-sectional research project. The quantitative research design was employed in the study, and the population and sample, data collection tools and data analysis were included in the method section.

The model of research is illustrated in Figure 1. The hypotheses of the research are given below, in accordance with the model.

Figure 1: Research Model

Source: Digital Transformation Readiness Survey Summary” by Center for Creative Leadership-Corporate Leaders, 2018

The present study sets out to examine the effect of digitalization on employee satisfaction and productivity at airports. In order to measure the effect of digitalization on these two factors, three hypotheses were developed. These hypotheses are outlined as follows:

- H1: The level of digitalization of the airport positively affects employee productivity.
- H2: Employee satisfaction is a mediating variable between digitalization and employee productivity.
- H3: The study hypothesizes that employee satisfaction, employee productivity and perception of the digitalization process vary according to demographic variables.

The population of this research consists of airport employees, and it was conducted using the survey technique. Convenience sampling was utilized in the research. 280 of the questionnaires addressed to

350 people were returned, and 269 forms were used in the study after the invalid forms were eliminated.

The research was conducted through the survey technique through the questionnaire questions presented to the employees of the airports. A questionnaire form consisting of four sections was used in the research. In the first part of the questionnaire form, demographic variables of airport employees are included. In the second part, employee satisfaction scale, in the third part, employee productivity scale and in the fourth part, digitalization process scale are included. Information about the scales is given below.

In order to measure employee satisfaction, the scale used by Demir (2014) in a postgraduate thesis research was used. The scale consists of 17 items and one dimension. The items in the scale are designed according to a 5-point Likert scale (1 - Strongly disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neutral, 4 - Agree, 5 - Strongly agree). Cronbach Alpha value of the scale is 0,949.

In order to measure employee productivity, the questionnaire translated from English to Turkish by Arıoğlu (2010) at Yeditepe University and used in his Master's thesis and analyzed for validity and reliability was used. The scale consists of 12 items and is designed according to a 5-point Likert scale (1 - Strongly disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neutral, 4 - Agree, 5 - Strongly agree). The reliability level of the scale (Cronbach Alpha) is 0,945.

The Digital Transformation Readiness Survey Summary scale, as employed by the Center for Creative Leadership-Corporate Leaders (2018), was utilized as the digitalization level scale. This scale employs a 5-point Likert system, ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). It comprises 11 items. The reliability level (Cronbach Alpha) of the scale is 0,971.

The research data were analyzed using statistical software. The reliability of the scales was assessed by deriving Cronbach Alpha values, while the suitability of the data for normal distribution was determined through the examination of skewness and kurtosis values. In addition, normality tests were performed. In the ensuing research, descriptive statistics were initially presented, followed by correlation analysis, regression analysis, and non-parametric group comparison tests (Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis). These analyses were conducted to ascertain the relationships between variables.

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of research conducted on the subject. In this context, firstly descriptive statistics are given and then the level of participation of the participants to the scale statements is evaluated. Subsequent analyses, employing correlation and regression techniques, were conducted to investigate the relationship and effects between variables. Finally, the results of group comparison tests are presented.

It was determined that 269 of the answered questionnaire forms met the appropriate and necessary conditions for the analysis to be made and were taken into consideration. The findings obtained in this direction and the evaluations related to the findings are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic findings

Category	Sub Category	Frequency	Category	Sub Category	Frequency
Gender	Male	177	Marital Status	Married	96
	Female	92		Single	173
Age	18-24	55	Education	Primary School	6
	25-34	142		Secondary Education	7
	35-44	47		High School	39
	45-64	24		Bachelor	190
	+65	1		Master's Degree	24
			PhD	3	

According to the findings given in Table 1, 65,79% of the respondents are male, 34,21% are female, 64,32% are single and 35,68% are married. When the distribution by age is analyzed, it is observed that 73,23% of the respondents are under the age of 34. According to these data, it can be said that

there are more young people employed in the sample. According to the education levels, it is understood that 70,63% of the participants have a bachelor's degree, 19,33% have a high school and primary education level and 10,04% have a postgraduate degree. Following this information, Table 2 presents the findings on the level of participation of the participants to the questions related to employee satisfaction.

Table 2: Frequency information about the level of participation in the statements of the Employee Satisfaction Scale

Items	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean	SD
ES1	9	24	34	131	71	3,86	1,016
ES2	11	28	43	118	69	3,77	1,072
ES3	9	26	40	127	67	3,81	1,026
ES4	8	18	40	111	92	3,97	1,014
ES5	10	10	17	110	122	4,20	0,981
ES6	4	5	4	62	194	4,62	0,746
ES7	4	6	14	100	145	4,40	0,811
ES8	4	9	49	124	83	4,01	0,872
ES9	2	10	12	106	139	4,38	0,799
ES10	11	15	36	102	105	4,02	1,058
ES11	17	30	44	102	76	3,71	1,175
ES12	9	21	64	109	66	3,75	1,019
ES13	7	12	26	116	108	4,14	0,946
ES14	8	17	68	100	76	3,81	1,012
ES15	8	10	31	131	89	4,05	0,929
ES16	7	17	41	113	91	3,98	0,990
ES17	10	5	30	118	106	4,13	0,949

As illustrated in Table 2, the frequency with which employees express satisfaction is measured on a scale from 1 to 5. The results of the survey questions on employee satisfaction indicate that the item with the highest level of strongly agree is ES6 (I endeavor to do my best in my job), with 194 votes. This finding suggests that employees are most effective in their roles. Conversely, ES12 (managers and employees trust each other in the organization where I work) received the lowest frequency of responses among the strongly agree statements.

The most positive statement for employee satisfaction was identified as 'I strive to do my best in my job' ($\bar{x}=4,62$). Conversely, employees have articulated more negative sentiments regarding the statement 'The management in the organization where I work appreciates the work performance' ($\bar{x}=3,71$) in comparison to the other statements on the scale. The results indicate that the majority of employees perceive that they strive to perform optimally at work. Concurrently, the employees' satisfaction with the management's recognition of their work performance at the workplace is found to be at a medium level.

Upon analysis of the standard deviations, it is evident that ES11 (The management in the company I work for appreciates the work performance) has the highest value, with a value of 1,175. This finding indicates that the variability in responses is greater than in the other categories. Conversely, ES6 (I endeavor to do my best in my job) exhibits the lowest standard deviation value of 0,746. This finding indicates that the level of participation in ES6 is comparable.

Table 3: Frequency information about the level of participation in Employee Productivity Scale statements

Items	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean	SD
EE1	3	5	26	114	121	4,28	0,802
EE2	4	7	24	108	126	4,28	0,848
EE3	2	3	10	103	151	4,48	0,694
EE4	5	20	32	105	107	4,07	0,990
EE5	10	10	33	108	108	4,09	1,001
EE6	2	4	11	114	138	4,42	0,711
EE7	2	4	5	100	158	4,52	0,683
EE8	2	5	6	104	152	4,48	0,705
EE9	3	3	5	82	176	4,58	0,695
EE10	6	5	11	120	127	4,33	0,827
EE11	2	5	5	117	140	4,44	0,697
EE12	3	3	7	98	158	4,51	0,710

As illustrated in Table 3, the frequency with which employees expressed concurrence with the statements pertaining to the employee productivity scale is documented. The results of the employee productivity survey indicate that the statement 'I fulfil my responsibilities' (EE9) received the highest number of responses, with 176 respondents expressing strong agreement. These results indicate that employees are attentive in completing the tasks they undertake. The lowest frequency strongly agree response is EE4 (I would like to undertake tasks beyond my responsibilities at work), with 107 responses. The responses to this question indicate a clear reluctance among employees to assume additional responsibilities beyond their designated roles, suggesting a preference for maintaining the scope of their existing duties.

The most positive statement for employee productivity, as determined by these findings, is EE9 'I fulfil my responsibilities' ($\bar{x}=4,58$). In contrast to the responses to EE9, employees expressed more negativity in response to EE4, with a mean score of 4,07. This indicates that employees have reservations regarding the proposition of assuming additional responsibilities beyond their current duties. The results indicate that the majority of employees believe that they fulfil their responsibilities. In addition to this, it is observed that the employees' opinions about "I would like to undertake tasks beyond my responsibilities at work" are moderate.

Upon analysis of the standard deviations, it is evident that EE5 (I am satisfied with the company I work for and the job I do) has the highest value, with a value of 1,001. This indicates that the responses are distributed significantly from the mean. Conversely, EE7 (I complete my work on time) exhibited the lowest standard deviation value of 0,683. This indicates that EE7 has responses that are proximate to the mean.

Table 4: Digitalization Process Frequency information about the level of participation in the scale statements

Items	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean	SD
DP1	6	6	17	103	137	4,33	0,868
DP2	2	6	38	122	101	4,17	0,805
DP3	5	10	34	123	97	4,10	0,892
DP4	7	14	38	112	98	4,04	0,975
DP5	8	12	37	123	89	4,01	0,958
DP6	5	13	47	111	93	4,02	0,940
DP7	7	15	38	116	93	4,01	0,973
DP8	8	11	36	117	97	4,06	0,962
DP9	11	14	34	116	94	4,00	1,028
DP10	6	15	36	113	99	4,06	0,962
DP11	6	11	39	120	93	4,05	0,925

As illustrated in Table 4, the frequency information concerning the level of agreement with the digitalization process scale statements is presented. According to the digitalization process questionnaire, the response that was given with the highest frequency was 'strongly agree' to DP1 (I believe that digital transformation in the enterprise I work for can be beneficial for the future of the enterprise). This finding is further corroborated by the observation that 137 responses were attributed to this particular item, thereby lending support to the notion that the provision of new technologies to businesses will result in an enhancement of productivity. Conversely, DP5, enquiring into the implementation of digital strategies for the purpose of evaluating the impact of innovations on the success of the enterprise, received the lowest frequency of responses, with a total of 89. This response indicates that the business has not yet fully transitioned to innovative digitalization movements in its strategies and that implementing innovative strategies will increase its success.

The findings indicate that the most positive statement in the digitalization process is DP1 'I believe that digital transformation in the enterprise I work for can be beneficial for the future of the enterprise' ($\bar{x}=4,33$). Conversely, employees have articulated more negative sentiments regarding the statement DP9 'The business I work for uses digital opportunities to increase the efficiency of employees' ($\bar{x}=4,00$) in comparison to the other statements on the scale. These results suggest that the majority of employees believe that digital transformation can be beneficial for the future of the business. Furthermore, the employees' views on the utilization of digital opportunities for enhancing employee productivity within their respective workplaces are moderate in nature.

A further analysis of the standard deviations reveals that the item 'My company uses digital facilities to increase employee productivity' (DP9) has the highest value, with a standard deviation of 1,028. This indicates that the responses are distributed significantly from the mean. The lowest standard deviation value is DP2 (The company I work for has knowledge about the impact of digitalization trends on competition) with 0,805. This value indicates that DP2 has responses that are above average. Following the presentation of findings related to the scale statements, descriptive statistics related to the scales are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics related to the scales

	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
ES	4,03	0,721	-1,221	2,353
EE	4,37	0,621	-1,973	7,234
DP	4,07	0,824	-1,084	1,395

Upon analysis of the descriptive statistics, the mean value of employee satisfaction is determined to be 4,03 (SD = 0,721), signifying a high level of satisfaction. The skewness value of -1,221 indicates that the distribution is skewed to the left, and the satisfaction level of the majority of the participants is above the average. The Kurtosis value of 2,353 points to a distribution that is peaked, suggesting the possibility of a concentration of extreme values. The variable pertaining to employee productivity has been found to have the highest mean value of 4,37 (SD = 0,621). This finding suggests that the participants have a positive perception of productivity. However, the skewness value of -1,973 indicates a strong left skewness, and the kurtosis value of 7,234 indicates an excessive density of extreme values. The mean of the digitalization process variable is 4.07 (SD = 0.824), indicating that the participants evaluate digitalization positively. The skewness value of -1,084 indicates a more balanced left skewness compared to the other variables, while the kurtosis value of 1,395 indicates that the distribution of extreme values is more balanced. These findings suggest that employees generally hold favorable views on satisfaction, productivity and digitalization processes. The skewness value, which is -1,084, indicates that the distribution is skewed to the left, suggesting that the data is concentrated at high values, with outliers potentially concentrated in certain variables. Table 6 presents the normality tests that analyze whether the variables are normally distributed.

Table 6: Normality test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
ES	,109	269	,000	,912	269	,000
EE	,157	269	,000	,816	269	,000
DP	,155	269	,000	,888	269	,000

The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests (all p-values <0,01) indicate that the variables do not meet the normality assumption. Consequently, the utilization of non-parametric tests becomes imperative. The subsequent table (Table 7) presents the correlation results of employee satisfaction, employee productivity and digitalization process variables.

Table 7: Correlation results

	ES	EE	DP
ES	1		
EE	0,756**	1	
DP	0,749**	0,685**	1

** p <0,01

The level of relationship between variables can be evaluated as weak between 0-0,29, moderate between 0,30-0,64, strong between 0,65-0,84, and very strong between 0,85-1 (Güngör & İlişen, 2018). According to the information in the table, there is a strong and significant positive relationship between Employee Satisfaction and Employee Productivity at the level of 0,756 (p < 0,01). There is a significant positive relationship of 0,749 between Employee Satisfaction and Digitalization Process. Finally, there is a significant relationship between Employee Productivity and Digitalization Process at the level of 0,685. Following the correlation tests, regression results are analyzed in Table 8.

Table 8: Regression results

Variables	Models (Dependent Variables)			
	1 (EE)	2 (EE)	3 (EE)	4 (ES)
DP	,685***	,270***		,749***
ES		,554***	,756***	
Observations	269	269	269	269
F	235,398***	202,383***	355,997***	340,344***
R ²	,469	,603	,571	,560
Adjusted R ²	,467	,600	,570	,559
Durbin-Watson	2,157	2,149	2,111	1,925

*** p<0,01

The regression analysis results evaluated the effects of the digitalization process on employee satisfaction and productivity. In the first model, the digitalization process was found to have a significant and positive effect on employee productivity ($\beta = .685$, $p < ,001$). The model explains 46,9% of the variance in employee productivity ($R^2 = ,469$, Adjusted $R^2 = ,467$). The model was found to be statistically significant in general ($F(1, 267) = 235,40$; $p < ,001$). In the second model, the effect of employee satisfaction and digitalization process on employee productivity was examined. Both variables were found to have a significant and positive effect on employee productivity ($\beta = ,270$, $p < ,001$; $\beta = ,554$, $p < ,001$). This model explains 60,3% of the variance in employee productivity (Adj. $R^2 = ,600$; $F(1, 267) = 202,38$; $p < ,001$). In the third model, the effect of employee satisfaction on employee productivity was examined alone and it was found that this relationship was stronger ($\beta = ,756$; $p < ,001$). The model explains 56,0% of the variance in employee productivity ($R^2 = ,560$, Adjusted $R^2 = ,559$; $F(1, 267) = 340,34$; $p < ,001$). The general conclusion obtained from the three models is that employee productivity has a partial mediating effect between employee satisfaction and digitalization process. The H_2 hypothesis developed in this context is accepted.

The fourth model discusses the effect of the digitalization process on employee satisfaction. The findings of this study demonstrate that the digitalization process exerts a substantial and positive influence on employee satisfaction, as evidenced by the statistical significance of the coefficient ($\beta = ,749$; $p < ,001$). The model demonstrates a high degree of explanatory power, accounting for 57,1% of the variance in employee satisfaction (Adj. $R^2 = ,570$; $F(1, 267) = 355,99$; $p < ,001$). This finding supports the hypothesis H_1 , which tests the positive effect of digitalization on employee productivity, and indicates that it is accepted.

In general, while the digitalization process exerts a significant effect on employee satisfaction and productivity, employee satisfaction emerges as the strongest predictor of employee productivity. The Durbin-Watson values ranging from 1,925 to 2,157 in the regression models indicate the absence of an autocorrelation problem (Yavuz, 2009). The results of the statistical test, presented in Table 9, indicate the presence of a significant relationship between the mean values of employee satisfaction, productivity and digitalization process, with respect to marital status and gender variables.

Table 9: Pairwise group comparison test results

H ₀ Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
The mean of Employee Satisfaction is the same across marital status categories.	Mann-Whitney U	,480	H ₀ Accept
Employee Productivity mean is the same across marital status categories.	Mann-Whitney U	,259	H ₀ Accept
The mean of Digitalization Process is the same across marital status categories.	Mann-Whitney U	,398	H ₀ Accept
Employee Satisfaction mean is the same across gender categories.	Mann-Whitney U	,747	H ₀ Accept
Employee Productivity mean is the same across gender categories.	Mann-Whitney U	,767	H ₀ Accept
Digitalization Process mean is the same across gender categories.	Mann-Whitney U	,879	H ₀ Accept

Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine whether there is a significant difference between the groups. No significant difference was found between employee satisfaction, productivity and digitalization process according to marital status and gender categories ($p > 0,05$). This shows that

these variables do not differ according to demographic factors. Table 10 shows the group difference tests according to age category.

Table 10: Group comparison test results by age category

	ES	EE	DP
Chi-Square	6,523	2,020	2,565
df	4	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	,163	,732	,633

In Table 10, Kruskal-Wallis tests were performed to determine whether age significantly differentiates the averages of employee satisfaction, employee productivity and digitalization process. No significant difference was found between age categories in any variable ($p > 0,05$). In Table 11, group difference tests according to education category will be given.

Table 11: Group comparison test results according to education category

	ES	EE	DP
Chi-Square	19,667	15,469	8,353
df	5	5	5
Asymp. Sig.	,001	,009	,138

In Table 11, Kruskal-Wallis tests were performed to determine whether the level of education creates a significant difference in the averages of employee satisfaction, employee productivity and digitalization perceptions. Accordingly, employee satisfaction ($p = 0,001$) and employee productivity ($p = 0,009$) differ significantly according to the level of education, but there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the digitalization process ($p = 0,138$). Hypothesis H_3 , which tests whether there is a significant difference in the averages of employee satisfaction, employee productivity and digitalization process according to selected categorical variables, is partially accepted.

5. Conclusion

The present study set out to ascertain the importance of digitalization at the airport, and the effect of the company's digitalization level on employee satisfaction and productivity. To this end, correlation and regression analyses were conducted. The findings of the correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between employee satisfaction and employee productivity (0,756), a strong positive relationship between employee satisfaction and the digitalization process (0,749), and a moderate positive relationship between employee productivity and digitalization (0,685). The regression analysis further substantiates the digitalization process's considerable impact on employee satisfaction and productivity, while employee satisfaction emerges as the predominant predictor of employee productivity.

The findings of the study demonstrate that hypotheses H_1 , H_2 and H_3 are confirmed. The study's findings indicate that digitalization in airports is a significant factor in employee productivity and satisfaction, and that investments in this area can enhance productivity, leading to increased growth and profitability. The study also provides sectoral and academic inferences in this direction.

The aviation industry is a field that requires the use of technological innovations with its structure open to continuous change and development. As one of the priority sectors that should follow the digitalization process, companies in this field are transitioning to modern digital systems to increase both passenger and employee satisfaction, gain competitive advantage and grow. However, in this transformation, it is critical that each company selects the systems suitable for its own needs, as not every innovation may be suitable for every company. In the digitalization process, it is important to adopt a human-centered approach without ignoring passenger expectations. In this process, organizing digitalization trainings for employees will increase the efficiency of the transformation by ensuring their rapid adaptation to new systems. While technological integrations reduce the workload, it should not be forgotten that the human factor always has an important place in the aviation industry.

A substantial corpus of academic research has been dedicated to the study of digitalization. A review of these studies reveals a paucity of research on the level of digitalization in the aviation sector in

relation to employee productivity and satisfaction. This research aims to address this lacuna in the existing literature by providing a comprehensive example for future studies. In this study, the effects of new concepts on employee productivity and satisfaction are examined in the context of digitalization, which is known to bring continuous innovation.

The present study was conducted with the objective of elucidating the significance of digitalization within the context of airports and its impact on employee satisfaction and productivity. The findings of the study indicated a positive correlation between digitalization levels and employee satisfaction and productivity. The study thus demonstrates that digitalization is an inevitable renewal process in the aviation sector, as in every sector under today's conditions. It has been determined that companies which integrate this process into every aspect of working life can achieve successful results in employee productivity and satisfaction. The present study has examined digitalization in detail and presented a novel and significant perspective on contemporary aviation.

The research has various limitations. A total of 350 people were asked a questionnaire in the research. The number of people who returned the questionnaire was 280, but the evaluation was carried out on 269 forms by removing the unsuitable forms. The fact that the sample group is only airport employees and consists of 269 forms gives the sample limit.

In future studies, the study can be expanded by examining the positive and negative effects of digitalization on employee stress level. In the regression analysis, it was concluded that the level of digitalization has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction and productivity, and other possible external factors were ignored. Adding another evaluation by considering other factors can also provide a different perspective to the research. In other studies that will examine the employee productivity and satisfaction of digitalization, the positive and negative effects of training programs on behalf of employees can also be observed. Finally, analyses such as the cost ratios of digitalization in the long and short term and the extent to which the cost will benefit can also be added. In this way, it is aimed that broader and guiding studies will contribute to both the literature and the sector.

Furthermore, the execution of prospective studies can be undertaken in both private and public institutions, thereby facilitating the acquisition of data pertaining to the distinctions and commonalities between these two entities. When this is considered more broadly, a survey study can be organized in two different universes, domestic and foreign, and it can be determined whether there are variations on a country basis.

Despite the existence of extant literature on employee productivity, employee satisfaction and digitalization, the scope of subsequent studies could be further expanded. Furthermore, the integration of diverse variables and the implementation of varied tests will facilitate the acquisition of data concerning the relationship between employee productivity, employee satisfaction and the digitalization process. In subsequent studies, the dependent and independent variables may be expanded, and the impact of altering these variables on the outcomes may be investigated. Given that the aviation sector is the primary focus of this study and that airports constitute the main focus of the study, comparisons can be made with different sector groups in this and similar evaluations.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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